

A NIGHT SKY TOURISM GUIDE

FOR EXISTING TOURISM BUSINESSES

Night sky tourism is any tourism activity that happens **outdoors at night**, and is aligned with principles of ecotourism and sustainable tourism. This guide is designed to help you come up with an interesting and locally relevant night sky activity that will attract guests to your area and stimulate the local economy.

For more resources and support, visit www.astrotourism.astro4dev.org or email astrotourism@astro4dev.org

ABOUT THIS GUIDE

The global ecotourism industry is forecast to reach \$374.2 billion in 2028.

Only 2 out of 10 people live under naturally dark skies.

This guide is designed to assist individuals and businesses experienced in daytime tourism in expanding their horizons into night sky tourism.

The global ecotourism industry worldwide was estimated at \$172.4 billion in 2022, and forecast to reach \$374.2 billion in 2028. The trend of experience tourism has been steadily rising over the past years, with the personalised travel and experiences market size estimated to reach \$447.3 billion globally by 2030. As these industries grow and become more competitive, it becomes important to imagine tourism products that appeal to travellers seeking these kinds of experiences, and to explore and reimagine various forms of tourism.

Nighttime is a relatively untapped tourism asset so far – Astrotourism is a relatively recent industry that has capitalised on the pristine dark skies in places to satiate their scientific curiosity about the night sky. While astrotourism is traditionally science-focused, this guide hopes to expand the definition of what is possible with the night sky and tourism by re-embedding our collective fascination with the night sky into a broader context that can align with ecotourism, cultural tourism, experience tourism, and sustainable tourism principles.

With an estimated 8 out of every 10 people living under light polluted skies, areas with low levels of light pollution have an incredible opportunity to offer travellers unique experiences. Nighttime activities also offer tour providers reduced competition compared to daytime activities, and almost all cultures have unique relationships to nighttime and the night sky, creating an ideal market opportunity for tourism activities at night.

Our hope is for this to be a reference point to guide existing tourism businesses in the implementation of night sky tourism products. Through this guide, we hope to empower you to create a unique and memorable night sky tourism experience to add to your offer to guests. By building sustainability, environmental consideration, and cultural and local relevance into your night sky experience, you will be in a better position to target the large market of travellers seeking authenticity and meaning in tourism, and generate revenue.

This guide will help you:

1. UNDERSTAND THE CONCEPT OF NIGHT SKY TOURISM, IN THE CONTEXT OF CURRENT TOURISM TRENDS.

2. ANALYSE YOUR LOCATION AND ITS POTENTIAL FOR NIGHT SKY TOURISM ACTIVITIES.

3. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENT A NIGHT SKY TOURISM EXPERIENCE THAT IS COHERENT WITH YOUR OTHER TOURISM ACTIVITIES.

4. MAKE EXPERIENCES MEANINGFUL THROUGH SUSTAINABILITY, ALTRUISM, AND DARK SKY CONSERVATION.

NIGHT SKY TOURISM, ASTROTOURISM, AND CELESTIAL TOURISM

Night sky tourism is a form of tourism that includes presence under the night sky and/or contemplation of the night sky. Night sky tourism encompasses astrotourism, which is also used interchangeably with (and includes activities of) celestial tourism.

Astrotourism typically involves the exploration of the night sky through the perspective of astronomy, with an emphasis on scientific interpretation of celestial objects.

Celestial tourism is observing naturally occurring celestial phenomena 'in the wild'. Activities can involve direct observation of events in the night sky like eclipses, meteor showers, or planetary transits.

While these activities fit into night sky tourism, the definition of *night sky tourism broadens the scope of activities from ones that focus on the night sky to ones that also harness the night sky as a backdrop for experiences.*

Including scientific astronomy in rural night sky tourism experiences is a great way to instil wonder and awe in visitors, but to enhance authenticity and local relevance, night sky tourism recommends combining the scientific information with local cultural and ecological heritage. Night sky tourism can also capitalise on celestial events by organising special events around them, but doesn't have to be limited to special celestial events. Night sky tourism can also involve other activities that don't necessarily focus on the night sky, but use the night as a backdrop for other activities. Natural darkness provides a platform for a variety of activities that can enhance other primary activities centred around food, wellness, or cultural exploration.

By disentangling nighttime experiences from a science-focused perspective to one that also honours local cultural perspectives and ecological assets, night sky tourism allows for activities that tap into the wonder of astronomy and the night sky while also aligning these activities with ecotourism and experience tourism tenets. This not only reaches a wider target of people than just science enthusiasts, but also allows tourism service providers to benefit from and diversify their offerings.

USEFUL DEFINITIONS/GLOSSARY

ASTROTOURISM

Astrotourism involves stargazing activities, visits to observatories, and educational experiences related to astronomy. It can also include celestial tourism, i.e. travelling to destinations specifically to observe celestial events, such as stars, planets, and other astronomical phenomena.

NIGHT SKY TOURISM

Night sky tourism refers to tourism activities that take place during the nighttime hours, focusing on experiences under the natural night sky. It includes stargazing, nocturnal wildlife tours, and other nighttime activities that leverage the darkness of rural or natural environments.

ECOTOURISM

Ecotourism is a form of sustainable tourism that emphasises responsible travel to natural areas, with a focus on conservation, environmental education, and the well-being of local communities. The goal is to minimise the impact on the environment while promoting conservation efforts.

CULTURAL TOURISM

Cultural tourism is travel focused on experiencing the cultural aspects of a destination, including its history, art, and traditions. It involves activities such as visiting museums, historical sites, festivals, and engaging with local customs and traditions.

SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

Sustainable tourism involves practices that minimise the negative impact of tourism on the environment, culture, and communities. It aims to preserve natural resources, support local economies, and provide meaningful and authentic experiences for visitors.

EXPERIENCE TOURISM

Experience tourism emphasises the creation of immersive and memorable experiences for travellers. It goes beyond traditional sightseeing and focuses on hands-on, participatory, and culturally enriching activities that allow visitors to deeply engage with the destination.

LEVERAGING YOUR ADVANTAGES AS AN EXISTING TOURISM BUSINESS

We recommend a Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations and Results (SOAR) analysis. This approach moves from a diagnostic to a dialogic perspective. A SOAR analysis will help you leverage your strengths as an existing tourism business as a strategic planning framework designed to focus on your business's positive attributes, harness available opportunities, articulate aspirations for the future, and ultimately achieve measurable results.

In the context of night sky tourism, this SOAR analysis begins with identifying your unique strengths as a tourism business. By recognising these **strengths**, you can build a strong foundation for your night sky tourism initiatives.

1. STRENGTHS

Existing Infrastructure: Leverage any existing infrastructure, facilities, or resources that can be repurposed for night sky tourism, such as accommodations, open spaces, or equipment storage.

Local Expertise: Tap into the knowledge and expertise of local guides, astronomers, or cultural experts who can enhance the authenticity and educational aspects of night sky experiences.

Customer Base: Utilise your established customer base from daytime activities to cross-promote and offer night time experiences, creating a seamless transition for visitors.

Night sky tourism presents many **opportunities**, such as minimal investment, low competition, growing interest in stargazing, potential for localisation, and the potential to expand your offerings.

2. OPPORTUNITIES

Low Competition: Recognize the relatively low competition in the night sky tourism sector compared to other daytime activities, offering a unique market niche to explore.

Growing Interest: Identify the increasing interest in stargazing, astronomy, and immersive nighttime experiences, aligning with the rising trend of ecotourism and sustainable travel.

Collaborations: Explore opportunities for collaborations with local astronomy clubs, educational institutions, and observatories to access specialised equipment and knowledge.

Aspirations are essential; they drive your vision for night sky tourism. Consider your long-term goals, like becoming a go-to destination for night sky experiences or making a positive impact on local communities.

3. ASPIRATIONS

Unique Offerings: Aim to create a range of unique, culturally immersive, and memorable nighttime experiences that set your business apart from competitors.

Community Involvement: Seek to engage with and support local communities through night sky tourism, contributing to their economic development and cultural preservation.

Education and Awareness: Aspire to educate visitors about the importance of preserving dark skies and raising awareness about light pollution's impact on the environment and human health.

Finally, the SOAR approach helps you set realistic targets and measure **results**, enabling you to track progress and adapt your strategies for optimal success in the night sky tourism sector.

4. RESULTS

KPIs: Establish key performance indicators such as visitor numbers, customer satisfaction ratings, revenue growth, and environmental impact measurements.

Continuous Improvement: Regularly review performance data and use it to fine-tune and optimise nighttime offerings to meet or exceed customer expectations.

Impact Assessment: Track the economic and social impact on the local community, including job creation and cultural preservation, to ensure alignment with aspirations.

EXPERIENCE TOURISM, ECOTOURISM, AND THE PURSUIT OF MEANING

In their paper The experience economy: micro trends, Yeoman and McMahon-Beattie report that experience tourism trends value “*escape from modernity to authenticity seeking... a craving for meaningful human interactions and a sense of belonging in a world dominated by technology drives the desire for immersive, intense, off-the-beaten track experiences*” – they “*enjoy finding products or experiences that have clear links to a place, time or culture – those that are produced in a traditional way, that are unique and that have a genuine story behind them*”. The experience driven tourism approach is a search for transformative moments that allow people to escape their own lives and view the world from another perspective, to achieve a temporary transcendence.

People express the narratives of their lives through the stories they collect, and meaningful tourism is a way to collect stories that are authentic and can be transformative.

Bjelajac, Đerčan and Kovačić define a meaningful tourism experience as one consisting of three parts: altruism, pleasure, and connection. The altruism aspect involves contributing to the improvement of conditions of a marginalised group, by contributing time or financial resources to these groups. Altruism can involve economically contributing to underdeveloped areas, either through the entire experience, or by incorporating elements into the experience that financially empower marginalised groups. The pleasure component of a well-being experience involves hedonism – witnessing beauty and experiencing relaxation. The third aspect, connection, involves the authenticity of the experience, and its immersive capacity, and giving the undertaker of the experience a feeling of connection to the landscape, the culture, the experience facilitator, and other attendees.

**A meaningful tourism experience consists of three parts:
altruism, pleasure, and connection**

The United Nations World Tourism Organisation defines ecotourism as nature-based forms of tourism involving the observation and appreciation of nature and the traditional cultures it hosts. In 2022, the global ecotourism industry was valued at 172.4 billion U.S. dollars, and it's anticipated to surge to 374.2 billion U.S. dollars by 2028. This growth is closely linked to the increasing importance of ecological and environmental considerations in the travel and tourism sector.

The 2021 WEF Travel & Tourism Development Report emphasises the pivotal role of natural and cultural resources in motivating travel. It also highlights a growing awareness among travellers of environmental risks, with climate action failure, extreme weather, and biodiversity loss ranking high among global concerns.

Eco-conscious travellers are aware of their impact on the planet, and are increasingly seeking environmentally sustainable options.

The intersection of these two sectors - travellers who pursue meaning, and travellers who want to experience the nature and culture of another place, inform the approach taken by this document to consider tourism happening at night as an opportunity for existing tourism providers to capitalise on these trends through night sky tourism.

ACTIVITY 1:

CREATING COHESION IN EXPERIENCES

Imagine a cultural immersion experience in a historic village. Activities like guided tours of heritage homes, traditional cooking classes, and storytelling sessions are carefully woven together. Each activity builds upon the last, creating a narrative that transports participants through time and culture. This cohesion ensures that visitors don't feel like they're simply jumping from one activity to the next; they're embarking on a meaningful journey, immersing themselves in the lives of the village's inhabitants. The result is a more profound and engaging experience, where every element serves a purpose, leaving them with a deep understanding of the village's rich history and traditions.

Cohesion in an experience enhances the visitor's journey.

This activity guides you analyse the themes in your current offerings, and come up with complementary activities for night sky tourism activities.

ANALYSING EXISTING THEMES

Before planning your astrotourism activities, it helps to analyse the existing themes in your activities and consider how new activities can align with these themes to create a cohesive visitor experience. Fill out the table below, using the examples in the table for reference and inspiration.

List Current Activities: List the activities and experiences you currently offer to daytime visitors.	Identify Current Themes: Examine these activities for overarching themes. These themes may include cultural heritage, ecotourism, adventure, wellness, or even a combination of two or more themes.	Visitor Expectations: Consider the expectations of your current visitors. What themes resonate with them? Note down these insights as they will be useful when designing your experience.	Considerations for Nighttime Activities: Write down some elements you can include in a nighttime experience to ensure cohesion across activities. What themes resonate with your visitors? Note down these insights as they will be useful when designing your experience.
Example: Daytime wildlife tours focused on local fauna.	Example: Wildlife and Nature Exploration	Example: Engaging with wildlife in its natural habitat	Example: Including nocturnal animals like owls, bats, and night-active mammals
Example: Daytime heritage tours	Example: Heritage Site Tours	Example: Delving into historical and cultural narratives, immersing themselves in the local lore and traditions	Example: Hosting evening storytelling sessions around a campfire or in historical settings, where local legends, historical anecdotes, and folklore about the night are shared, deepening the cultural immersion.
Example: Daytime yoga and meditation workshops centred on relaxation and mindfulness	Example: Wellness and Relaxation	Example: Experiencing a holistic approach to relaxation	Example: Moonlit meditation sessions under the stars, incorporating the calming influence of the night sky. See our Astronomy for Mental Health flagship for more inspiration
Example: Daytime outdoor adventures	Example: Adventure and Outdoor Activities	Example: Experiencing a sense of adventure, exploration, and engagement	Example: Nighttime campfire gatherings and guided night hikes
Example: Daytime cooking classes focused on culinary skills	Example: Culinary Experiences	Example: A comprehensive culinary experience, including obtaining skills and getting opportunities to taste diverse local flavors	Example: Outdoor food tastings in the dark, Nighttime foraging under the stars.
Your activities:	Your current themes:	Your visitor expectations:	Your elements:

ACTIVITY 2: ANALYSING EXISTING RESOURCES

Before delving into the practical implementation of astrotourism and night sky tourism, it helps to flesh out the existing resources that are specific to your environment, and to understand the constraints your specific environment puts on what you can offer.

Nighttime tourism activities are influenced by weather conditions and light pollution levels, and the activities in this section help you to get a sense of what these are at your location, and how they influence the kinds of activities you can implement.

Resources that you can leverage to create an immersive experience are ecological resources and cultural resources, which will help align your nighttime tourism offering with principles of ecotourism and cultural tourism. You can incorporate these literally through the location or context of the experience, or even include them in more subtle ways like through your branding, logo design, or naming of the experience.

1. ASSESSING CONDITIONS FOR ASTROTOURISM

A. Analysing Seasonal Patterns, Cloud Cover, Rainfall, and Humidity Levels

This section helps you to understand the weather conditions in your geographical area and their impact on astrotourism and night sky tourism activities. Visit weatherspark.com/ to gather the following data, and fill out the table on the following page.

1. Use the arrow in the top left to change the units on the top left to °C, km/h.
2. Type in the name of your city into the Search bar and press 'Enter'.

3. Scroll down to the 'Average Temperature in City' section, fill in the numbers from the 'Low' column into the 'Minimum temperature' row in the table.

Average	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
High	26°C	27°C	26°C	25°C	23°C	22°C	22°C	23°C	25°C	25°C	24°C	24°C
Temp.	20°C	21°C	21°C	20°C	19°C	18°C	17°C	17°C	19°C	20°C	19°C	19°C
Low	15°C	15°C	16°C	16°C	15°C	13°C	13°C	13°C	13°C	15°C	16°C	15°C

4. Scroll down to the 'Clouds' section, and fill in the percentages from the 'Cloudier' row into the 'Cloud cover' row.

Fraction	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Cloudier	68%	70%	71%	73%	64%	61%	54%	48%	48%	61%	62%	63%
Clearer	32%	30%	29%	27%	36%	39%	46%	52%	52%	39%	38%	37%

5. Scroll down to the 'Precipitation' section and fill in the data from the table into the 'Days of Rainfall' row.

Days of	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Rain	4.6d	3.6d	7.9d	13.3d	8.7d	1.7d	1.0d	1.5d	1.7d	6.6d	11.5d	7.4d

6. Scroll down to the 'Sun' section, and fill in the percentages from the table into the 'Hours of daylight' row.

Hours of	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Daylight	12.2h	12.2h	12.1h	12.1h	12.1h	12.0h	12.1h	12.1h	12.1h	12.1h	12.2h	12.2h

7. Scroll down to the 'Humidity' section, and fill in the percentages from the table into the 'Humidity' row.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Muggy days	0.0d											

Sample Table

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Minimum temperature	15°C	15°C	16°C	16°C	15°C	13°C	13°C	13°C	13°C	15°C	16°C	15°C
Cloud cover	68%	70%	71%	73%	64%	61%	54%	48%	48%	61%	62%	63%
Days of rainfall	4.6d	3.6d	7.9d	13.3 d	8.7d	1.7d	1.0d	1.5d	1.7d	6.6d	11.5d	7.4d
Hours of daylight	12.2 h	12.2 h	12.1 h	12.1 h	12.1 h	12.0 h	12.1 h	12.1 h	12.1 h	12.1 h	12.2 h	12.2 h
Days of humidity	0.0d											

Fill out this table:

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Minimum temperature												
Cloud cover												
Days of rainfall												
Hours of daylight												
Days of humidity												

Now you will go through each row of the table to help you understand what you should consider given the conditions in your particular area. Make notes in the 'Notes' box on the next page. *You will also refer back to this section as you fill out the 'Accessibility and Constraints' section.*

Minimum temperature

Most places reach minimum temperature at night, so this is a good indication of how cold it gets outdoors at night. Keep in mind that this temperature doesn't account for wind, so guests may feel colder. If your minimum temperature is around 15°C or higher for most of the year, you are in a good position to host an activity outdoors. Also keep in mind that your guests will feel colder if they are sitting still, and will get warmer if the activity involves a lot of movement. Make a note of any special clothing or items they will need to bring (e.g. windbreakers, warm clothing), and what you can provide (e.g. blankets) to make them comfortable.

Cloud cover

Clouds obscure the moon and stars in the night sky, so if you have a cloud cover level of below 50% for most of the year, you are in a good position to offer activities that focus on elements of the night sky like the moon and stars. Depending on how dark your location is you can include equipment (see astronomy for tourism section). Excessive cloud cover limits your ability to include the moon and stars directly, but you can still consider activities with a different focus (e.g. food tastings, storytelling) that take place outdoors at night that include night sky themes, or leverage the sensory changes that occur in natural darkness..

Days of rainfall

Rainfall obviously limits the amount of time you can spend outside at night. If there are months where you have more than 15 days of rainfall, consider implementing your activity indoors. With any astrotourism and night sky tourism activity, it's important to have a backup for bad weather, but in areas with rainfall it is especially pertinent.

Hours of daylight

In places that experience seasons, days with longer nights are best suited to nighttime activities, so guests have enough time to get a good night's sleep. In many places, summer (longer days) is the primary tourism season, so offering nighttime activities in winter when nights are longer can help to generate revenue during low season. Keep in mind that longer nights are also associated with colder temperatures.

Humidity

The level of moisture in the air dictates how clear and sharp the view of the moon and stars are. If you are in a place with less than 5 humid days a month, this is a good place to offer activities that focus on the night sky, since the view of the moon and stars is crisp and clear. If, on the other hand, you have a lot of humid days, you are better off with an activity that doesn't directly focus on the night sky, but uses the night as a background for a different focus.

Notes

Monitoring the weather conditions

While this activity will help you understand broader weather conditions and appropriate seasons for night sky tourism over the year, it's important to keep monitoring the weather up to the time of your activity, especially if it will be outdoors or involve observing the night sky.

Most smartphones have a built-in weather app, which you can use to check the weather in the days and hours leading up to your experience. The website timeanddate.com/weather/ also allows you to see a long term and day by day/hour by hour forecast of the weather.

Later in this guide, you will also develop a Poor Weather Policy to ensure you have a clear plan for dealing with unfavourable weather conditions near the time of a planned and scheduled experience.

B. Estimating Light Pollution Levels

Light pollution (excessive, misdirected, or obtrusive artificial light) brightens the night sky, masking the light from fainter stars and planets. Assessing the level of light pollution in your chosen location is crucial for a successful astrotourism experience. Light pollution can significantly affect stargazing visibility and the overall visitor experience.

Option 1: Estimating Light Pollution Levels Online

Find your general location on the map at lightpollutionmap.info by typing your address into the search bar or navigating through the map manually. What colour filter is there over the area? Match the colour to a number on the chart below and note it down in the box below. These colours/numbers indicate the levels of light pollution of the sites and will be important during the experience design. 1 is the lowest, and 10 is the highest level of light pollution.

Option 2: Estimating Light Pollution Levels Using the Bortle Scale

The Bortle Scale is a widely accepted tool for assessing light pollution levels. It classifies skies into nine categories, from Class 1 (pristine, dark skies) to Class 9 (inner-city skies with severe light pollution). You can use [this online flowchart](#) to conduct field observations at night to assess the impact of light pollution in your area. While the flowchart contains some terms that may require some knowledge of astronomy, the terms are easily searchable. You can also enlist the help of an amateur astronomer if you have access to one.

Interpreting the results

Areas with low levels of light pollution offer good views of stars, galaxies, deep sky objects, and fainter objects in the night sky. Such skies are rare for travellers, and given the appropriate weather, you might want to prioritise outdoor activities that allow visitors to experience the dark skies directly, either through activities under them or using equipment like binoculars and telescopes.

If your location is very bright and light polluted, you should consider using the night as a background rather than a focus for your activity, placing the emphasis on other aspects of the activity. If you want to offer an astronomy specific activity, consider including additional interpretation tools and interfaces between people and the sky, in the form of storytelling, presentations, or indoor night-sky related infrastructure that aligns with your themes. If you want people to engage with the night sky, your focus is best kept to the Moon, bright planets, and other brighter objects in the night sky, and would benefit from the inclusion of binoculars or telescopes.

Note down the level of light pollution, and how this affects the kind of astrotourism/night sky tourism experience you can offer at night.

Natural Landscapes

Consider the natural beauty of your location. Is it situated in a region with clear, dark skies? Are there nearby wilderness areas, parks, or nature reserves that are safe (from both people and wildlife) to visit at night? Identify potential location/s to include in your experience.

Biodiversity

Does your area have unique flora and fauna that come to life at night? Wildlife sightings, such as nocturnal animals or migrating birds, can enhance nocturnal experiences. Make a list of nocturnal animals that can safely be seen at night. You might benefit from consulting a local wildlife expert about this.

Geological, Water and Landscape Features

Bodies of water, like lakes, rivers, or ponds, can create stunning reflections of the night sky, adding a touch of magic to astrotourism experiences. Make a list of any bodies of water that you may be able to include in your experience.

Unique geological rock formations, can serve as intriguing venues for nighttime activities, including storytelling or moonlit hikes. List any such formations if you have access to any at nighttime around your area.

List any special or iconic features of the landscape (e.g., big/old trees, mountains, large rocks with specific shapes) that are significant to the local area.

Is the landscape rocky or flat? Is it an open area or is the horizon blocked by buildings, trees, or other obstacles? How much of the sky can you see in which direction? This might also constrain the activity you implement (e.g limited walking, or conducting the experience facing a particular direction)

Safety Considerations and Special Equipment

Are there any threats from people or animals outdoors at night (e.g. crime, wild animals, poisonous insects)? Is there anything you can do to mitigate these threats?

Do people need to bring special clothing items or other things (eg. mosquito repellent, red head lamps, warm clothing)?

IDENTIFYING CULTURAL RESOURCES

Local Traditions

Think about local cultural traditions and stories associated with nighttime or the night sky in your region. Are there myths, legends, or historical events related to celestial phenomena that you can incorporate into your experiences? Seek out individuals with expertise in local culture, folklore, or indigenous knowledge related to the night sky. Collaborating with cultural experts can enrich your offerings with authentic narratives and traditions.

Heritage Sites

Are there any nearby heritage sites or historical landmarks that can serve as backdrops for cultural and astrotourism experiences?

Local Art and Artisans

Are there local artists and artisans you can engage with to create night sky-inspired artwork or crafts? Their work can be featured in your experiences, adding a cultural dimension.

Cultural astronomy

List any indigenous stories about the night sky, nighttime, or general culture. Some resources to look through are [here](#) and [here](#). You can also reach out to the IAU National Outreach Coordinator for your region to help you source this information, as well as to local cultural experts.

ACTIVITY 3: DESIGNING THE EXPERIENCE

By now you should have a clear idea of what's possible within your location in terms of night sky activities, and you will have fleshed out any ecological and cultural resources that may be of use.

After analysing your existing themes and resources, the next step is to design a cohesive night sky tourism experience that blends in with your established offerings. This section provides guidance on how to craft a memorable and engaging nighttime experiences for your visitors.

THEMATIC, LOCATION, AND NARRATIVE ASPECTS

Theme Integration

Visit the 'Analysing Existing Themes' section and note down the most appropriate activity idea that come to mind. Keep in mind the constraints that you determined in given your unique context as you filled out in the table. Incorporate astrotourism elements that complement and enrich your existing themes. Ensure that the experience aligns with the overarching theme of your location.

Storytelling

Whether it's cultural, ecological, or wellness-focused, stories can create a powerful emotional connection. Identify a central idea that you want your experience to communicate.

For an overview of how to create an engaging story in tourism, we recommend going through pages 22-25 of '[A Design Manual for Astrotourism Experiences](#)'. If you have the time, you can also work through this manual in its entirety as it is a valuable resource for astrotourism experience design.

Tying the experience to the local landscape and culture

Identify a suitable location for this activity. Refer to the 'Identifying Ecological Assets' section you filled out earlier for this. You can also make note of special features of your landscape identified in this section for branding, marketing, logo design, or even naming the experience.

What cultural elements from your earlier research can you include in your activity? Refer to the 'Identifying Cultural Assets' section for this. Do your best to include local cultural astronomy information in particular, especially if your experience is astronomy-focused, since it helps to expose visitors to multiple perspectives of the night sky and offers visitors a very unique perspective.

IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCES

Include physical cultural touchpoints

Symbols and objects from the local culture lend an air of authenticity and uniqueness to an experience. Try to include cultural crafts, motifs, patterns, and elements to ground the experience in a local framework. Are there any cultural or locally made objects you can include in the experience?

Utilise natural darkness to engage the senses

The most memorable experiences are ones that engage multiple senses. At night, human vision naturally becomes weaker, and other senses are heightened. Consider sensory elements of the experience outside of visual ones that you can draw visitors' attention to during the experience (e.g. sounds of nature, traditional music, textures, smells).

Food

Food is a great way to engage multiple senses and to enhance authenticity by grounding the experience in a local context. Consider using foods, spices and herbs that grow locally, and include local rituals, medicinal foods and special dishes if you can.

Interactive Components

Introduce hands-on activities that encourage participation and learning. For example, visitors can learn to identify constellations, use telescopes, or even participate in celestial-themed arts and crafts.

**FILL OUT THE WORKSHEET ON THE FOLLOWING PAGE TO
SYNTHESISE THIS INFORMATION INTO AN EXPERIENCE**

WHERE WILL THIS EXPERIENCE TAKE PLACE?

CULTURAL ELEMENTS TO INCLUDE

THE CENTRAL
IDEA TO
COMMUNICATE

YOUR EXPERIENCE

PHYSICAL CULTURAL
TOUCHPOINTS TO INCLUDE

HANDS-ON ACTIVITIES
TO INCLUDE

CAN NATURAL
DARKNESS ENHANCE
THIS EXPERIENCE? HOW?

CAN YOU USE
FOOD OR
BEVERAGES TO
ENHANCE THIS
EXPERIENCE?
HOW?

POOR WEATHER POLICY

Decide what you will do in case the weather is unfavourable for the night sky tourism activity you have planned. Some ideas to explore are to reschedule the session, provide a refund, or come up with a similar fallback activity that can be done in an indoor location as well. If you decide to choose a backup activity indoors, make sure you adhere to the relevant safety and comfort guidelines below in both locations.

SAFETY AND COMFORT

Do your best to ensure that your experience takes place in as safe a setting as possible, with everything in place to ensure visitor comfort, or to at least mentally prepare them for any discomfort. Here are some considerations:

Temperature

Nighttime temperatures are generally much colder than during the day, and wind can make it feel even colder. Consider providing comfortable seating, warm clothing or blankets, heaters, or hot beverages and snacks for outdoor nighttime activities.

Ecological threats and preparation

If you live in an ecologically diverse area, there may be a higher number of bugs and mosquitoes at night. Recommending long protective clothing to participants, and providing an insect repellent that isn't damaging to living creatures is something you should consider. If there is danger from any other living creatures and there are precautions that guests can take (e.g. not bringing particular food items, not making noise), please inform them beforehand.

Visibility, lighting, and fear of the dark

Visibility at night is greatly reduced due to the design of human eyes, and although the experience requires darkness, some people may be nervous or afraid of the dark and feel more comfortable with lighting.

Briefing visitors about what exactly to expect at which stage of the experience can help mitigate their safety concerns greatly.

Make sure to carry a source of red light with you (e.g. red head lamps) - red light is the least damaging to the nocturnal environment, and it doesn't destroy human dark adaptation so people will still be able to see the stars effectively.

If you do need to use light on pathways or in particular areas, make sure these lights are night sky friendly by using warm colour temperature bulbs, shielding the light, and linking it to sensors or timers so it's off when not in use. Refer to the Dark Sky Friendly Lighting page in the Astronomy Resources section for more information on how to use light at night responsibly.

Emergencies

Create an emergency plan with contacts and an exit plan in case of illness or emergencies (including sudden weather changes). It is also recommended to carry a basic first aid kit and prepare yourself with knowledge of what to do for common illnesses or injuries that may occur.

ASTRONOMY RESOURCES

If you are planning to implement a more astronomy-focused experience, the following pages contain some resources and information to help you include an astronomy component into your experience.

RESOURCES FOR PLANNING

Stellarium

Stellarium is a powerful tool for tourism providers to learn about the night sky and plan future stargazing events. This user-friendly software provides a detailed simulation of the night sky, offering a comprehensive view of stars, planets, and constellations. You can use Stellarium to familiarise yourself with the night sky's layout. The desktop and web apps allow you to plan for future events by letting you skip ahead to specific dates and times. You can also change settings to view the constellations of different cultures and their star lore, which will help you find and include locally relevant cultural astronomy information.

[Stellarium Web](http://stellarium-web.org) – stellarium-web.org

[Stellarium Desktop](http://stellarium.org) – stellarium.org

[A video tutorial for beginners](https://bit.ly/4eXLS4W) - bit.ly/4eXLS4W

timeanddate.com/astronomy

An invaluable website to help you plan for celestial highlights is the [astronomy section of timeanddate.com](http://timeanddate.com/astronomy). This website shows you various upcoming night sky events including meteor showers, eclipses, planet positions and moon phases. You also get location-specific information about visibility, timings, and extra tips.

EQUIPMENT

Handheld binoculars

Binoculars are a great beginner astronomy instrument with a shallow learning curve, and can help to elevate the stargazing experience. These portable devices bring the wonders of the night sky closer, making celestial objects more vivid and detailed, like a tiny telescope. You can use binoculars to enhance guided stargazing sessions, allowing guests to explore constellations, planets, and other celestial phenomena with greater clarity. Providing binoculars as part of a stargazing package or tour adds an interactive element, enabling visitors to actively explore the night sky.

Recommendation: 10x50 binoculars offer the best image to weight ratio – they are easy to hold up for long periods and work well in areas that are light polluted as well. Some pairs that you can explore are:

[Celestron UpClose G2 10x50 Binoculars](#)

[SVBONY SV206 10x50 Binoculars](#)

[Bushnell Legacy WP Binoculars](#)

[Nikon ACULON A211 10X50 Binoculars](#)

Optional: A normal camera tripod with a [binocular mount](#) will let you mount the binoculars and stargaze hands-free. You can also get a [smartphone photo mount](#) that attaches to this set-up for guests to take photos of celestial objects with their smartphones.

**BINOCULAR
MOUNT**

**SMARTPHONE PHOTO
MOUNT**

Mounted binoculars provide stable, hands-free viewing, making it easier to see details without shake or strain. This improves comfort and enables longer observation sessions, especially for faint objects.

Mounted binoculars

20x65 and/or 20x80 astronomical binoculars are easy to maneuver, give clear images, and don't require special maintenance. For diverse audiences, the most useful accessory is a parallelogram (see below); this will allow you to quickly adjust the height of the binoculars while maintaining the same viewing perspective.

[Celestron SkyMaster Pro 20x80 Binoculars](#)
[Oberwerk 20x65 ED Deluxe Binoculars](#)

Parallelogram mount

Parallelogram mounts allow easy adjustment of the height of mounted binoculars, which can help with comfortable viewing for people of different heights and reduce neck strain during extended sky-watching sessions.

[Celestron SkyMaster Pro 20x80 Binoculars](#)
[Oberwerk 20x65 ED Deluxe Binoculars](#)

Telescopes

A reflector telescope offers the best balance of affordability, durability, and versatility. An 8-inch reflector telescope with a Dobsonian mount is the most ideal for easy use and viewing a wide range of objects. These telescopes need to be aligned (collimated) before each use. They typically come with two eyepieces, one for a wider angle view and another for higher magnification. Reflectors are common in tourism settings, and having a range of eyepieces helps adapt to different observations.

Small Telescopes

Best for observing solar system objects. These telescopes are table-top telescopes and will need a separate tripod, or a flat, stable surface to be mounted on, and a tripod can be purchased separately. These telescopes will be easy to use and show you enough detail if you are in a light polluted area.

[Zhumell Z114](#)

[Orion SkyScanner 100mm Reflector](#)

[Orion StarBlast 4.5 Reflector](#)

[Sky-Watcher Heritage 130p](#)

[Sky-Watcher Heritage 150p](#)

Larger Telescopes

These are entry level Dobsonian telescopes which can be used to observe solar system objects as well as deep sky objects. These are best used in a dark site, but easy to learn to use and disassemble to pack for travel in a car.

[Orion XT6 Classic Dobsonian](#)

[Apertura DT6 Dobsonian](#)

[Sky-Watcher 6" Traditional Dobsonian](#)

[Orion XT8 Classic Dobsonian](#)

[Apertura AD8 Dobsonian](#)

[Sky-Watcher 8" Traditional Dobsonian](#)

BEGINNER TARGETS

Meteor showers

Meteor showers tend to attract a lot of public attention. Observing constellations and meteor showers does not require any special equipment, and they can have strong impact on engagement.

The targets below are aimed at a beginner level of observing, and are great for audiences that are not familiar with astronomy, or haven't used a telescope before. If you are just starting to develop astrotourism experiences, we recommend focusing on this level.

Recommendation: Limit new information and concepts to three or fewer to avoid confusion, as processing new knowledge requires cognitive energy.

An optimal beginner observing experience can be set up with the following objects (in order): the Moon, Jupiter, Saturn, notable constellations, and if sky conditions allow it, some zodiacal constellations.

The Moon

The Moon is an ideal telescope object for first time viewers, and easy to find in the night sky. You can mention some names of its surface features like seas and craters (no more than 5) to make the observation more interesting. The Moon is a great target for both binoculars and telescopes.

Tip: Paste [a map of the Moon](#) with its features onto the telescope – it will help you not have to memorise details, and give people waiting to observe something to read and learn.

When the Moon is more than half illuminated, telescopes labeled APO or ED work better to reduce chromatic aberration (surrounding bands of red, blue, or yellow light) from the Moon's bright light.

Saturn and Jupiter

Saturn and Jupiter are the most striking planets to view through a telescope.

Saturn's rings are visible through a telescope. Its largest moon, Titan, can also be seen as a small point of light nearby.

Through binoculars, Jupiter is visible as a bright spot with four Jupiter's cloud bands are visible in shades of light and dark. Its four largest moons shift positions each night, making it different every time you observe it.

INTERPRETATION TOOLS

Mobile stargazing apps

Mobile stargazing apps, or Sky map apps, make exploring the night sky easy and fun. These apps use your phone to show names and details of stars and planets when you point it at the sky. You can use these apps to learn the night sky on your own, to guide guests during stargazing sessions, or even provide devices with the app for guests to explore on their own.

For iOS devices:

[Stellarium Mobile](#) (paid)

[Night Sky](#) (free)

[Classic Sky Map 2](#) (free)

[Sky Guide](#) (free)

For Android devices:

[Stellarium Mobile](#) (paid)

[Sky Map](#) (free)

[Star Walk 2](#) (free, also has a [paid version](#) without ads)

[Sky View Lite](#) (free)

Laser pointer

Laser pointer: to point out stars and constellations, to show people where to look.

Do some research before getting a laser pointer, and learn to use them safely. They can blind people or wildlife instantly, and also distract flying planes. They are illegal or strictly regulated in many places, so make sure to follow your local laws carefully.

Printable star maps

You can get printable monthly sky maps at [this link](https://skymaps.com/downloads.html) (skymaps.com/downloads.html), based on whether you are located in the Northern Hemisphere, at the Equator, or in the Southern Hemisphere. You can use these to plan your own stargazing events, or leave them out for guests to explore the night sky on their own in the evenings.

DARK SKY FRIENDLY LIGHTING

Dark sky friendly lighting is a way to ensure the best view of the night sky and the protection of the nocturnal environment from your location. A good guideline is to modify your outdoor lighting fixtures to follow [DarkSky International's Five Lighting Principles for Responsible Outdoor Lighting](#):

Five Lighting Principles for Responsible Outdoor Lighting

Responsible outdoor lighting is	<p>1 Useful</p> <p>Use light only if it is needed</p> <p>All light should have a clear purpose. Consider how the use of light will impact the area, including wildlife and their habitats.</p>	
	<p>2 Targeted</p> <p>Direct light so it falls only where it is needed</p> <p>Use shielding and careful aiming to target the direction of the light beam so that it points downward and does not spill beyond where it is needed.</p>	
	<p>3 Low Level</p> <p>Light should be no brighter than necessary</p> <p>Use the lowest light level required. Be mindful of surface conditions, as some surfaces may reflect more light into the night sky than intended.</p>	
	<p>4 Controlled</p> <p>Use light only when it is needed</p> <p>Use controls such as timers or motion detectors to ensure that light is available when it is needed, dimmed when possible, and turned off when not needed.</p>	
	<p>5 Warm-colored</p> <p>Use warmer color lights where possible</p> <p>Limit the amount of shorter wavelength (blue-violet) light to the least amount needed.</p>	

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For a more thorough inventory, use DarkSky International's [Home Lighting Assessment](#) on your property to inventory your lighting and make appropriate changes for the best view of the night sky and stars. You qualify for a certificate after submitting your application, and can look into applying for other Dark Sky Place designations if your location qualifies and you manage to leverage community support.

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FINAL WORDS

Thank you for using this guide - we hope you found it helpful! By designing cohesive astrotourism experiences that build on existing themes, immerse visitors in multi-sensory engagement, celebrate celestial highlights, and prioritise safety and comfort, you'll create memorable nighttime adventures that seamlessly integrate with your daytime offerings.

For more resources and support, visit astrotourism.astro4dev.org, or email us at astrotourism@astro4dev.org.

**PLEASE SCAN THIS
QR CODE TO GIVE US
YOUR FEEDBACK ON
THIS RESOURCE**

